

New physics-LSTM hybrid models for control-oriented glucose prediction in Type 1 Diabetes*

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Abstract—Glucose modelling is crucial for an efficient management of Type 1 Diabetes (T1D). In recent years Neural Networks (NNs) techniques, in particular Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs), have shown very promising performances in glucose prediction. However, to use them in control application, these NNs have to be able to correctly learn the effect of each single input from the data. Considering that meals and insulin boluses characterizing the datasets occur simultaneously, the pure NNs are often unable to distinguish their effects. This work proposes two Physics-LSTM hybrid Models (PhLSTMs) merging a classical Black Box model (BB) with two LSTM-based approaches in order to obtain satisfactory prediction capabilities also for single impulse responses to insulin/meal. The resulting PhLSTMs have been tested on a case study of 2 *in silico* patients showing satisfactory glycemic prediction performances both on real-life datasets and impulse responses to insulin/meal.

I. INTRODUCTION

Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) is an autoimmune disease characterized by insulin deficiency with consequent constant high Blood Glucose levels (BG), called hyperglycemia, a condition associated with long-term damages related to eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, and blood vessels [1]. In order to avoid them, patients with T1D need exogenous insulin administration to keep the BG in the safe range (70 - 180 mg/dl). In recent years, the treatment of T1D has been revolutionized by the so-called Artificial Pancreas (AP), a closed-loop system which automatically regulates the BG concentration by providing the proper amount of insulin to infuse through a subcutaneous (SC) insulin pump and basing its decision on glucose data, measured by Continuous Glucose Monitoring sensor (CGM), and other patient's information [2]. SC devices, although convenient being minimally invasive, introduce delays in insulin action that require particular attention especially at meal times. To compensate for the meal, the patient has to estimate and announce the amount of carbohydrates (CHO) to the controller to allow a more immediate response and obtain better postprandial glycemic control, leading to a so-called Hybrid Closed-Loop (HCL) approach.

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Glucose-insulin models play a crucial role in the development of new technologies for T1D therapy: in fact the development of model-based control algorithms, of alarm systems for the prevention of critical events and of fault detection systems all rely on glucose-insulin models. For example, the Model Predictive Control [3] algorithm exploits a model to predict glucose and compute the optimal insulin therapy. In order to prevent hypo and hyperglycemia events and preserve the patients safety, AP can be equipped by prediction-based alarm systems that rely on patient models to evaluate the risk beforehand allowing the patient to intervene in advance [4], [5], [6], [7]. In order to detect faults, like unannounced meals, models can also be used to detect unexpected glucose trends.

Model identification for T1D patients is extremely difficult due to the noisiness of the data, the nonlinearities of the system and, above all, the fact that the main inputs (insulin and meals) have opposite effects on the output (BG) and occur almost simultaneously. In literature several model identification methods are present. Classical identification methods include, for example, the identification of linear Black-Box models (BBs) described by two Transfer Functions (TFs) to represent the patient's BG response to insulin and meals, respectively. The BBs can be obtained by linearizing general compartmental models obtained with broad clinical parameters and subsequently customised for each patient with his/her own data [8]. Other approaches identify a personalized BB directly from data with no intermediate steps [6], [9]. The great advantage of using linear models is that they are intelligible and thus it is possible to force constraints regarding the response to insulin and meals (e.g. gains) based on clinical experience. This clinical knowledge is difficult to extract from the data with general identification methods due to the synchronous effects of the inputs. The limitations of these models is their inability to capture the nonlinearities present when dealing with real patient dynamics, an example is the dawn phenomena (which refers to rising glycemia during dawn time) or their unreliability for dynamics far from equilibrium (e.g. in hyper- or hypoglycemia) where prediction precision is crucial. Another model category includes Neural Networks (NNs) trained with Machine Learning (ML) techniques. In recent years ML techniques have achieved remarkable results in various fields comprising the model identification one. NNs are universal approximators and thus have the potential to capture all nonlinearities present in the considered systems. Many ML techniques have been proposed for glucose-insulin model identification. For example, in [10], [11], kernel methods are

used to model nonlinear relationships mapping the input data into a high-dimensional feature space and carrying out the training with various types of regressions like kernel or support vector. Other techniques use a Multi Layer Perceptron (MLP) to combine in a non linear way an auto regressive model and exogenous signals [12].

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have proved to be suited for time series prediction due to their internal architecture that enables to correlate data between different time steps. Among these Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs) have emerged as being performant with various configuration like single-ones [6], [7], stacked LSTM [13] and in Sequence to Sequence (Seq2Seq) [14], [15], [16]. However, on the base of the prediction purpose, different specifics are required to the models: if a model is used for alarm systems it is sufficient that the overall glycemic prediction is accurate; while if the prediction is used in a control problem, it is necessary not only that the predicted signal is close to the real one, but that the model responds correctly to individual inputs, thus that the impulse responses of the glucose-insulin model are well identified. A glucose-insulin model that ensures a good impulse response to individual insulin bolus and meal intake can be an effective tool in predicting the effects of therapy variations and so it can be effectively used in optimal therapy definition. To the best of our knowledge, in most of the works present in the literature the evaluation of the prediction performance does not take into account the effects of individual inputs but considers only the overall glycemic signal [15], [16], [17]. In this work, classical LSTM-based approaches established in literature have been evaluated on single impulse response to insulin/meal showing not satisfactory performances. Then, a new Physics-LSTM hybrid Model (PhLSTM) is proposed: LSTM-based approaches are combined with a classical BB with the aim of capturing the advantages of each method and improve the impulse responses prediction needed for control applications.

II. METHODS

A. Single Personalized-LSTM approach for AP

LSTMs are special type of RNNs. The structure of a RNN is characterized by a recurrent loop where the output of a node is fed-back as input to the next temporal replica of the node, propagating in this way long term dependencies through time. LSTMs are particularly well-suited for modeling sequential data because they are equipped with internal memory cells that address the issue of vanishing gradients [18] that allow them to capture long-range dependencies in the data more effectively [19]. Mathematically a single memory cell (Fig. 1) is defined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} c_k &= f(u_k, h_{k-1}) \times c_{k-1} + i(u_k, h_{k-1}) \times \tilde{c}(u_k, h_{k-1}) \\ h_k &= o(u_k, h_{k-1}) \times \tanh(c_k) \end{cases}$$

where $c_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c}$ is the internal cell state at time k , $h_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c}$ the hidden state, with n_c the dimension of the cell state that is equal to the number of LSTM neurons. $u_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is the

Fig. 1. Scheme of a single LSTM-cell.

input, with n_u the number of features. \times is the Hadamard product and \tanh is the hyperbolic tangent, used as activation function. The self-loop of the cell is composed by four gates f, i, \tilde{c} and o which add or remove information to modify the value of the cell state: f , the forget gate, determines which information is removed from the cell state c_k ; i , the input gate, decides which value of the cell state c_k is updated; \tilde{c} , the input activation gate, creates a new candidate value of the cell state c_k ; o , the output gate, determines which information contained in the cell state c_k goes in output.

The four gates are described by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_k, h_{k-1}) &= \sigma(W_f u_k + U_f h_{k-1} + b_f) \\ i(u_k, h_{k-1}) &= \sigma(W_i u_k + U_i h_{k-1} + b_i) \\ \tilde{c}(u_k, h_{k-1}) &= \tanh(W_c u_k + U_c h_{k-1} + b_c) \\ o(u_k, h_{k-1}) &= \sigma(W_o u_k + U_o h_{k-1} + b_o) \end{aligned}$$

where $W_f, W_i, W_o, W_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times n_u}$ are the input weight matrices, $U_f, U_i, U_o, U_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times n_c}$ are the previous output weight matrices and $b_f, b_i, b_o, b_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times 1}$ are the biases, with σ the sigmoid function. The LSTM can be composed by one or more layers, and each layer by a certain number of neurons n_c . The output of the second last layer is passed to the last one, called fully connected (FC) layer to obtain the final output of the network \hat{y}_k :

$$\hat{y}_k = W_y h_k + b_y$$

where $W_y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p \times n_c}$ is the matrix of the output weight, with n_p the number of outputs of the network, and b_y the bias. Considering the significant inter-patient variability, in this work the hyperparameters of the single LSTM are selected individually for each patient leading to Single Personalized-LSTM (SP-LSTM) [5], [7]. The proposed SP-LSTM is characterized by a single layer and a FC layer,

Fig. 2. Scheme of LSTM-cells in a Seq2Seq configuration.

with four inputs ($n_u = 4$) and one output ($n_p = 1$). The inputs u_k are the past glucose values $CGM(k - PH)$ of PH minutes before, with $PH = 60$ minutes; the injected insulin through an insulin pump considering basal insulin, $b(k)$, and bolus, $B(k)$, separately, and the meals provided to the patient, $M(k)$, $u_k = [CGM(k - PH), b(k), B(k), M(k)]$. An estimate of $M(k)$ is available since a HCL is implemented and the output \hat{y}_k is the estimated glucose value at the current time, $\hat{G}(k)$. The number of neurons n_c is used for the personalization of the network.

B. Sequence to Sequence approach for AP

Seq2Seq is a NN configuration comprising two components: the encoder, which receives as inputs sequences of values and maps them into a high-dimensional space, and the decoder, which receives the encoded sequence and decodes it into a prediction sequence. In practice, during training the encoder learns to design its own features and the decoder to use them to make predictions. The proposed Seq2Seq uses LSTMs both in encoder and decoder and has already found applications in glucose prediction [14], [16], [15].

The structure of the Seq2Seq is reported in Fig. 2. The encoder receives as inputs EN patient's samples of past recorded data ($EN = 5$ hours) like CGM , b , B and M and it encodes them in a state representation $\{c, h\}$ at the considered present time k . The decoder receives the encoded sequence and future readings of b , B and M and predicts future glucose sequence up to PH samples, $[\hat{G}(k) \cdots \hat{G}(k + PH)]$. Each output of the LSTM cells in the decoder (hidden state), passes through a FC layer, their results are regarded as the decoder's glucose prediction.

C. Physics-LSTM hybrid models for control-oriented prediction

In presence of simultaneous inputs, classical LSTM-based approaches can have difficulties in understanding single input effect. Therefore this paper proposes a new PhLSTM that merges the BBs with the classical LSTM-based ones. BB encapsulates all a priori knowledges about each single input (clinical parameters, system gains, dynamics, etc...), but it is not able to represent nonlinear effects. The LSTM-based

Fig. 3. Configuration of a Physics-LSTM hybrid Model (PhLSTM).

approach, on the other hand, is able to learn nonlinearities, time-variant trends and everything that the BB lacks to represent, even though it cannot discern the effect of each input. The BB considered in this paper is the Impulse Response (IR) model reported in [6], [9] and it is obtained by identifying the TFs correlating insulin and meal inputs to the glycemic output. The BB is a multi input single output system composed by seven poles (four representative of the insulin effect and three of the meal one) and two gains (one for each input) for a total of nine variables. Initially, two impulse response scenarios are simulated and used in a minimization problem, to obtain a population model. Then, it is personalized to the specific patients via a constrained optimization using real-life datasets. In order to test the robustness of the proposed hybrid method, a BB identified for a generic patient of the simulator is here used to predict the glucose trend of other patients. However, this model showed good generalization properties for the overall diabetic population, so it has been chosen to generate predictions reference \hat{G}_{BB} .

The integration between the BB and the classical LSTM-based approach is carried out, as showed in Fig. 3, in a sequential manner by giving ΔCGM (the deviation of the past CGM data with respect to glucose predicted by BB, \hat{G}_{BB}) as input to the LSTM-based approach. Both LSTM-based and classical BB make prediction from the current time instant k till future prediction horizon PH : the BB predicts also future glycemia while the LSTM-based approach estimates future glucose deviation due to the uncertainties of the BB ($\Delta \hat{G}_{LSTM}$). \hat{G}_{BB} is then corrected by $\Delta \hat{G}_{LSTM}$ and the result \hat{G} consists in the future prediction of the new hybrid model.

III. DATASETS AND PERFORMANCE METRICS

A. UVA/Padova Simulator

The proposed work has been developed using the UVA/Padova simulator [20], [21], a metabolic simulator approved by the Food and Drugs Administration (FDA) as an alternative to animal trials in the pre-clinical testing of control strategies for diabetes management. The simulator includes a population of 100 adult patients that effectively represent the metabolic behavior of the entire diabetic population. This work focused on a case study of 2 patients (A

and B) that showed behaviours of interest for the presented work.

B. Datasets and signal processing

Six different datasets have been used to train the networks and to evaluate their performances: a training dataset (tr-dt) lasting 24 days is used to train the models that contains untreated snacks, unannounced meals, late meals or insulin bolus to make networks aware of unexpected situations. A validation dataset (v-dt) of 10 days is used to tune the hyperparameters and four different testing datasets to evaluate different capabilities of the networks. The first testing dataset (ts-dt1) lasts 7 days and is characterized by a meal scenario extracted by the same distribution of the tr-dt. The second one (ts-dt2) lasts 7 days and has a more challenging meal distribution, generated by a probabilistic model that describes the habits of the average Italian T1D subject [22], with the aim of testing the robustness of the networks under different conditions from those seen in tr-dt. The other 2 testing datasets last 1 day and evaluate the impulsive response to insulin (ts-dtI) and to meal intake (ts-dtM). In particular in ts-dtI, the insulin impulse corresponds to the patient-specific insulin bolus amount computed by the controller at 12:00 to compensate a meal of 30 grams; in ts-dtM an untreated meal of 50 grams is assumed at 12:00. The meal distribution in the various scenarios is described in Table I as mean (\pm SD) or median [25^{th} , 75^{th}] percentiles if data are normally or not normally distributed, respectively.

TABLE I
DATASET SCENARIO DESCRIPTION

	Meals	CHO	Time
tr-dt	Breakfast	41.9 (\pm 12g)	07:04 (\pm 17 min)
	Lunch	51.9 (\pm 7.9g)	12:33 (\pm 18 min)
	Dinner	72.7 (\pm 10.86g)	19:33 (\pm 18 min)
	Snacks	18 [7.5g 25g]	
v-dt	Breakfast	41.3 (\pm 7.47g)	07:02 (\pm 19.9 min)
	Lunch	51.7 (\pm 9.2g)	12:33 (\pm 20 min)
	Dinner	72.3 (\pm 13.1g)	12:33 (\pm 20 min)
	Snacks	18 [7.5g 25g]	
ts-dt1	Breakfast	50 (\pm 25g)	08:00 (\pm 60 min)
	Lunch	60 (\pm 30g)	13:00 (\pm 60 min)
	Dinner	70 (\pm 35g)	60:00 (\pm 60 min)
ts-dt2	Breakfast	45.3g (\pm 3.6g)	08:25 (\pm 60 min)
	Lunch	60.3g (\pm 3.2g)	13:25 (\pm 63 min)
	Dinner	74g [26g, 77g]	20:43(\pm 56 min)
	Snacks	20g (\pm 5g)	

C. Training

Both SP-LSTM and Seq2Seq are trained using Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) optimizer to perform the back propagation algorithm, with the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the actual signal (y) and its prediction (\hat{y}) used as

loss function: $MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$. The training has been carried out using a computer equipped with a GPU NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1050, an Intel i7-7700HQ CPU with 2.80 GHz and 32.0 GB memory. Regarding SP-LSTMs, α and the number of epochs n_e are optimized for each patient; they vary in the intervals [0.001 0.01] with step of 0.01 and [32 512] with step of 32, respectively. The training of the SP-LSTMs is implemented with TensorFlow and Keras API, and the hyperparameters are optimized using KerasTuner. The Seq2Seq is implemented in Pytorch version 2.3.1, the dimension of the hidden state is 200 while batch size is 128, the number of epochs is 500 and learning rate is 1×10^{-4} with early stopping.

D. Performance indexes

In order to evaluate the prediction performances of the proposed methods, different metrics have to be defined:

- the index of fitting (FIT), a normalized index that indicates how much the prediction matches the real data. Perfect prediction corresponds to FIT equal to 100%, which decreases with deterioration of the quality of the prediction. It can also take negative values:

$$FIT = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N \|\hat{y}_k - y_k\|}{\sum_{k=1}^N \|y_k - \bar{y}\|} \right)$$

- the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) that quantifies the variance of the prediction error. The smaller the RMSE, the better the prediction:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (y_k - \hat{y}_k)^2}$$

where \bar{y} is the mean of y and $\|\cdot\|$ the norm of the signal; N is the total number of samples of y .

IV. RESULTS

The prediction performances of all the models introduced in this work are reported in Table II for two in-silico case studies (patient A and patient B).

Considering patient A, the SP-LSTM tested with ts-dt1 has good prediction performances with a FIT of 59.59%, these results are in line with the literature [15], [16]. The SP-PhLSTM, tested with the same dataset, has still good prediction performances (FIT = 52.74%) with a negligible decrease of 11.5%. On the other hand, if these models are tested with the more challenging ts-dt2, the SP-LSTM achieves a FIT of 35.32% while the SP-PhLSTM seems to be more robust to diet variations with a FIT of 42.44%. The same considerations can be drawn for the Seq2Seq which obtains on ts-dt1 and ts-dt2 a FIT of 61.25% and of 50.35%, respectively. These performances with the S2S-PhLSTM slightly decrease but are still satisfactory (FIT = 52.26% and FIT = 30.48%). BB obtains poor results on ts-dt1 (FIT = 12.39%) and even worse on ts-dt2 with a negative FIT of -13.42%. These model performances can be confirmed also observing the predicted profiles reported in Fig. 4, where it is possible to note how all the proposed

TABLE II
RESULTS

	Patient	Model	ts-dt1	ts-dt2	ts-dtI	ts-dtM
FIT	A	BB	12.39	-13.42	-10.53	-117.43
		SP-LSTM	59.59	35.32	-17.72	32.61
		SP-PhLSTM	52.74	42.44	34.52	12.55
		Seq2Seq	61.25	50.35	-63.55	21.88
		S2S-PhLSTM	52.26	30.48	25.91	13.84
	B	BB	16.16	12.59	10.95	-37.34
		SP-LSTM	66.60	43.58	-38.90	36.45
		SP-PhLSTM	62.96	15.80	-49.24	21.24
		Seq2Seq	62.01	42.65	-49.05	24.64
		S2S-PhLSTM	59.18	24.65	51.46	30.28
RMSE	A	BB	27.52	39.43	25.11	75.45
		SP-LSTM	11.85	21.13	26.52	22.91
		SP-PhLSTM	13.86	18.8	14.74	29.73
		Seq2Seq	12.17	17.26	37.16	27.1
		S2S-PhLSTM	15	24.17	16.83	29.9
	B	BB	21.04	25.11	12.76	40.87
		SP-LSTM	7.92	15.40	18.31	19.09
		SP-PhLSTM	8.78	22.98	19.68	23.65
		Seq2Seq	9.53	16.47	21.35	22.43
		S2S-PhLSTM	10.54	21.65	6.95	20.75

approaches show satisfactory performances when evaluated on the ts-dt2. The BB is the only model that fails in capturing the meal responses of patient A, but, considering that it has been identified on another patient, these performances were expected. If no additional tests were put in place, all the results obtained would be quite satisfactory and suggest that all models have a clear understanding of the real physical relationship between inputs and output with the best one being a plain Seq2Seq model. By testing the models on ts-dtI and ts-dtM a different picture emerges: the SP-LSTM obtains a FIT of -17.72% and 32.61% on insulin and meal response, respectively, and the Seq2Seq a FIT of -63.55% and 21.88%. These results show that classical LSTM-based approaches fail to understand the physical relationship between inputs and output when trained with synchronous inputs. The seemingly good results obtained by these models on the first two tests (ts-dt1 and ts-dt2) are not a robust indicator of their prediction performances since they probably learn the joint effect of both inputs but they are not able to distinguish each contribution. The impulse response tests (ts-dtI and ts-dtM) show how only the meal effect is properly learnt by classical LSTM-based approaches to make predictions while the insulin effect is not understood. Having a model with good understanding of the insulin effect is important for all applications, particularly in control-oriented ones where the insulin delivery has to be optimized. The PhLSTMs instead retain positive values in both impulse tests: the SP-PhLSTM reaches a FIT of 34.52% and 12.55% and the

Fig. 4. Model prediction on ts-dt2 for patient A: all methods show satisfactory performances apart from BB.

S2S-PhLSTM a FIT of 25.91% and 13.84%, respectively. Although the performances related to the meal impulse response decrease by 49.13% on average, the ones related to the insulin response are improved by 217.79%. It is also worth to be noted that BB shows not adequate performances in particular for the meal response test, reaching an extremely low FIT of -117.43%: here PhLSTMs have good ability to compensate for this negative starting point, with an average FIT improvement of 111.2%. The selection of a BB with better meal performances would improve these results.

Considering the patient B, the performances of the classical LSTM-based approaches are similar to those of the patient A, showing good results for the first two datasets, but poor performances in the overall impulse responses. The peculiarity of this patient is that the SP-PhLSTM unexpectedly obtains worse performance on all the datasets with respect to its classical LSTM-based version; this point requires additional investigations. On the other hand, the S2S-PhLSTM reaches good prediction performances on both the impulse response tests, in particular for the insulin one obtaining a FIT of 51.46%. Looking at the insulin impulse response (Fig. 5) it can be observed that the BB is able to understand the descending effect of the insulin but with a completely different sensitivity with respect to the considered patient. The other models can not predict the glucose trend, except for S2S-PhLSTM (blue solid line) which shows a satisfactory representation of the insulin effect. By looking at all the results it can be highlighted that the classical LSTM-based approaches are not able to distinguish the effects of the single insulin and meal inputs. The proposed PhLSTMs can be a promising method to overcome this problem: S2S-PhLSTM demonstrates good performances for both patient A and B, while SP-PhLSTM seems a bit less robust to inter-patient variability obtaining good results only for patient A.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper new PhLSTMs for glucose prediction are proposed and compared with classical LSTM-based approaches present in literature; the PhLSTMs exploit both the poten-

Fig. 5. Model prediction on ts-dtI for patient B: the BB improves Seq2Seq performances (blue solid line) but it is not sufficient in SP-PhLSTM (orange solid line).

tiality of the LSTMs, able to predict the complex dynamics and nonlinearity of the T1D patient, and of classical BBs, which base their prediction on a priori knowledge. Their performances are assessed on classical test sets and on impulse response datasets consisting of the impulse response to single insulin bolus and meal. Impulse response tests, often overlooked, are a more robust way to expose learning errors compared to classical ones. In fact, considering the glucose predictions for two patients taken as case-study, both classical LSTM-based approaches and PhLSTMs achieve good performance indexes on the classical ts-dt1 and ts-dt2; these results taken on their own would suggest that all the models are able to adequately understand the inputs-output relationship of the system. On the other hand, considering ts-dtI and ts-dtM, it can be seen that SP-LSTM and Seq2Seq show a drastic drop in the performances related to the insulin response, highlighting that these classical LSTM-based approaches actually fail to understand the individual effect of insulin/meal. It is then impossible to use these models for control-oriented tasks where their predictions are used to compute the optimal insulin amount to be administered to the patient. On the contrary, the proposed physics-LSTM hybrid models are able to learn the effect of each input with an acceptable decrease of the overall prediction performances on the real-life datasets. The preliminary results reported in this paper suggest that the Seq2Seq approach could be more robust to inter-patient variability when combined with the BB. Additional tests are required to verify this assumption extending this approach to the entire 100 subjects of the in-silico population of the UVA/Padova Simulator. Future developments will include a patient-tailored tuning of the Seq2Seq approach and the use of a patient-tailored BB to manage the high inter-patient variability.

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